

Beyond Topicality: How do Social and Life Scientists Select What to Read?

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1. Introduction

Topicality is widely recognized as the most influential criterion in relevance evaluation (Green, 1995; Huang, 2009; Macedo-Rouet et al., 2012; Saracevic, 2016; Wang & Soergel, 1998; Xu & Chen, 2006). While topicality is nearly universal across any retrieval contexts, other relevance criteria have been shown to be more context-specific (e.g., Cool et al. (1993)) or determined by user characteristics such as domain knowledge (Cole et al., 2011; Dinet et al., 2010; Sihvonen & Vakkari, 2004). Academic search engines must therefore accommodate the fact that different disciplines are shaped by distinct epistemic cultures – that is, field-specific configurations of how knowledge is produced and validated (Knorr-Cetina, 1999) – which manifest in various publication and reception practices likely to influence search and relevance evaluation behavior. This poster investigates domain-specific patterns in relevance evaluation by contrasting the behavior of researchers from social and life sciences.

2. Method

Fifty researchers participated in this online user study: 25 from medicine-related life sciences (e.g., biomedicine, biophysics) and 25 from social sciences (especially sociology and political sciences), spanning all career levels (8 professors, 31 postdocs, 11 predocs), with 22 women and 28 men. A prefabricated SERP mimicking Google Scholar presented ten articles with linked abstracts. Working on three tasks, participants selected up to three documents for reading while screen sharing and thinking aloud via Zoom. Think-aloud data were deductively coded. The code system was developed by merging and grouping previously reported relevance criteria (Barry, 1994; Barry & Schamber, 1998; Saracevic, 2016; Wang & Soergel, 1998). Following a qualitative content analysis, Barnard's unconditional test was used to analyze binary group differences, as it offers greater statistical power than the conditional Fisher test, particularly in small samples.

3. Results

Overall, relevance evaluation was based on a vast array of 53 relevance criteria mentioned at least once in both groups (social and life sciences). Initial qualitative content analysis shows broad similarity across disciplines: participants from both fields primarily used *titles* and *abstracts* to assess relevance, spending most time reading the latter. When reading the abstract, topic- and content-oriented relevance criteria, such as *approach*, *topical match*, *scope*, *data basis*, *clarity* and *topic* (each mentioned by 75-100% of participants), were mentioned with similar frequency across fields, confirming the centrality of topicality.

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Figure 1: Disciplinary Differences in Abstract Reading

Disciplinary differences became evident beyond topicality. The PCA biplot in Figure 1 reveals that participants from the social sciences cluster on the right side of the first component (Dim1), aligning with the relevance criteria *research culture*, *discipline*, *publication date*, *references* and *understanding*. All of these were mentioned more frequently by social than life scientists when reading abstracts (cf. Table 1) with *research culture* reaching statistical significance ($p = 0.044$) and *publication date* and *understanding* approaching significance ($p = 0.055$).

Table 1

Share of participants mentioning relevance criteria

Relevance Criteria	Social Scientists	Life Scientists	Barnard's test (p-value)
abstract length	8%	44%	0.002
discipline	72%	44%	0.153
mental effort	12%	40%	0.016
publication date	72%	48%	0.055
references	52%	32%	0.102
research culture	52%	24%	0.044
understanding	56%	28%	0.055

By contrast, life science participants appear in the lower quadrants of the biplot, in the direction of *abstract length* and *mental effort*. These criteria were also mentioned significantly more often in this group ($p = 0.002$ and $p = 0.016$, respectively; cf. Table 1). Together, these results suggest that social scientists prioritize situating a paper within an academic discourse (*discipline*, *references*, *publication date*) emphasize their own scholarly expertise (*research culture*, *understanding*), whereas life scientists tended to be more sensitive to reading effort (*abstract length*, *mental effort*).

4. Discussion and Conclusion

This comparative analysis of relevance evaluation behavior of researchers in the social and life sciences demonstrates that while core topic-related criteria remain stable across fields, differing epistemic cultures shape the use of additional relevance criteria, particularly when reading abstracts. These criteria may even prove more decisive to relevance judgments than topicality itself.

The study underscores the importance of designing retrieval systems that account for domain-specific relevance evaluation behavior. While social scientists may benefit from systems supporting the discursive contextualization of research works, a focus on enhancing user performance and cognitive efficiency – perhaps through summarization or highlighting of a study's data basis – may be better suited to life scientists.

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